

DEVELOPMENT TENDENCIES OF THE ECONOMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Annotation : In the article Uzbekistan Republic of the economy formation stages seeing will be released . Socio-economic growth of their pace more development statement in Uzbekistan small business and private entrepreneurship development growth analysis done Economical of development present stages given .

Key words : economy, small business, development, Uzbekistan Republic .

Annotation. The article considers the stages of formation of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The further development of socio-economic growth is described, the growth in the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan is analyzed. The modern stages of economic development are presented.

Key words: economy, small business, development, Republic of Uzbekistan.

Next in years Uzbekistan economy fast is developing . The economy more development in 2017-2021 Uzbekistan Republic development according to Actions in the strategy defined important from directions is one In it macroeconomic stability and economy and his networks stable growth to the pace reach, structural and institutional reforms dredging, mineral raw material resources deep again work at the expense of work being released of products competitiveness increase, regions, districts and cities potential development, rapid development in the eye caught

To independence After achieving the reforms the first stage to the end According to entrepreneurs class formation, competition environment, market infrastructure and market relations the basics Create for conditions creator normative legal base was formed . At this stage administrative command system country economy effect consequences eliminate reach with together, new economic relationships was born and entrepreneurs development for Small business fast development and private entrepreneurship of the state each bilaterally support with privatization and from monopoly release processes with together take went So in 1994 to the end 54 thousand enterprise own economy forms changed 34 percent of them private, 48 percent shareholding society, 16 percent to the team, 1 percent for rent converted . in 1995 country in the economy non-state sector share growth as a result 44 percent of industry, rural economy 97 percent of its products non-state sector enterprises and farmer in farms, non-state in the sector work released trade field about 82 % organize did. in Uzbekistan done increased of reforms next, second stage finance sector strengthening and to stabilize directed was As a result economy in the composition new networks appear it happened To the real sector of the economy attraction done foreign investments volume from 10 billion dollars increased from that only in 1996 from 3.6 billion dollars in itself excess mastered, as a result our country fuel and energy and grain independence provided, industry

strengthened . State from stability stable economic to grow transition for conditions to create succeeded it happened

Stable economic to grow transition from 1998 to 2000 has been of reforms the third stage . At this stage modern of the economy foundation was created, macroeconomic to stability achieved, new institutions and management organs Create according to big affairs done increased Finance, tax and money systems fundamentally to changes met Only 1998 during gross internal product volume of 4.4 percent, industry work output to 5.8 percent, rural economy - by 4% . in 1998 of the world many developed in the states happened gave financial crisis of Uzbekistan financial industry to the situation effect without doing castle didn't get it . But it is economical reforms done in raising of the republic advanced movement stop didn't get it . In this period state from the disposal release process continue did in 1999 gross internal in the product non-state of the sector share is 64.5 percent, 64 percent in industry, rural 98.7 percent of the farm is privatized in enterprises 74.2 percent of the population was employed . So so foreign to sources according to, at the end of the 90s of the 20th century industry work release growth pace according to our republic is the CIS countries between the first from places one took : 117 percent in 1999, in Russia and for 1991 compared to this the indicator was 45%, Ukraine - 44%, Kazakhstan - 41% . in 2000 in Uzbekistan industry work release volume is 1 trillion . 980,6 billion soums .

Since 2000 deep structural changes economic of growth solution doer to the factor became Industry of the product main growth new organize done enterprises at the expense of provided . Investments common from 56 percent of the volume excess new work release networks to develop directed . Situation to the analysis Based on Uzbekistan leadership this stage to the liberal system suitable coming next reforms as marked .

Uzbekistan economy development present stage in 2008 started and until now continue is doing He is the world financial and economic of the crisis Beginning with is described " Uzbek" of progress to the principles of the model action to do result has been Uzbekistan external trade of circulation a lot network structure the world economic of the crisis expansion conditions reliable it happened In the Republic done being increased To the crisis against measures program (2009-2015) of the crisis heavy in the conditions of the economy stability provide and more to develop directed measures are the most important social programs continue in progress efficiency manifestation did This is the population employment and well-being to increase directed . Prestigious the world economic forum to the rating according to Uzbekistan in 2016-2017 of the world economy is the fastest grew up five state to the line enters High Assembly of chambers on December 14, 2016 joint at the meeting to the word came out Uzbekistan Republic President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev the following noted : " Networks and regions modernization make, their competitiveness increase, export potential development always our attention in the center will be Of this for all to areas foreign investments and advanced technologies, including information communication technologies more active attraction reach necessary Exactly that's it basically we are going to 2030 gross internal product 2 times the size more than to increase reach we will get it gross internal of the product such to growth reach for average yearly growth rate of 4.8 percent provide that 's enough at the time past year during last 11 years inside in the country GDP growth at least 8 % organize did. Announcement done to forecasts according to the republic gross internal of the product growth pace 2018 during continue is enough and by 2023 and 8.8 percent organize that 's enough while positive of dynamics continue that it will means That's it with

together, population soul per head gross internal product in 2018 up to 1973 dollars, according to the forecast according to 2023 up to \$ 2329 grows .

Uzbekistan Central Asia of the region industry developed from the republics is one 24% of GDP near in industry is formed . Uzbekistan the most in the region network to the economy have Central Asia countries by work issued common final product in share Uzbekistan share, State statistics committee information According to, 80 percent of mineral fertilizers are chemical 94 percent of the fiber is natural 54 percent of gas is natural 59 percent of gas . from cement, 65% cotton from raw materials . So in Uzbekistan economic of reforms all stages state leader role plays And today's in the day state help directed advanced structural changes, our society his life update processes continue carry on and deepening potential, stability and safety more to upgrade strong impulse national the economy development, country of the population life quality more improve the most important purpose social projects done is increasing .

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